

YŷT:633.631.527

PLANTS ON A PROMISING FEED THAT INCREASES THE YIELD OF NATURAL SAGITTARIUS.

¹ Nazarov X.T., ² Khalilov X.T., ³ Mamayusupov Sh.X., ⁴ Suloymonov Sh.A.

1. Associate Professor of Samarkand State University.

2. Senior Research Fellow, Karakol and Desert Ecology Research Institute

3. Student of Samarkand State University.

4. Student of Samarkand State University.

Annotation. *The article discusses the introduction of pasture forage plants from different soil-climatic regions of Central Asia and their use to enrich and increase the productivity of natural pastures.*

Keywords. *Introduction, sample, coltsfoot, natural pasture, artificial pasture, agrophytosinosis, desert, adyr.*

Relevance of the topic. The largest share of natural pastures is located in the coastal regions of the Republic. However, their productivity is very low and fluctuates sharply depending on climatic conditions. In addition, pastures are in a state of crisis due to non-compliance with the necessary rules of pasture use, which leads to a sharp decline in biodiversity in desert and hilly pastures, a decrease in pasture productivity and deterioration of feed quality. Therefore, one of the most urgent tasks today is to improve the condition and increase the productivity of natural pastures in crisis (Mahmudov et al.).

Pasture forage plants in the experimental field "Nurota" of the Research Institute of Karakul and Desert Ecology in the phytomelioration of natural pastures using high-yielding forage species as a "living" gene pool. It is advisable to use promising varieties.

In particular, the addition of high-yielding plant species rich in protein and the most important nutrients to the newly created artificial pastures will not only increase the

productivity of pastures, but also enrich the pastures with new plant species (Khalilov et al. 2020.)

Source and methods of research. The source quality of the study was light gray soils of the Nurata hills, ephemeral-ephemeroid-type pasture-fed pasture forage plants. Planned field experiments, phenological observations, biometric measurements were carried out based on the use of generally accepted methods in botany and plant introduction. The results of the study and their evaluation. The research was conducted at the Nurota Experimental Field of the Karakol and Desert Ecology Research Institute. The study site is located in the lower foothills of the Nurata Range, at an altitude of 660-680 meters above sea level.

Due to the remoteness of the Nurata oasis from open water basins and its direct connection with the Kyzylkum Desert, the climate is characterized by a sharp continental and arid drought.

The perennial average temperature is 13.80C, fluctuating over the years; the absolute maximum was recorded at +46.7 o C and the absolute minimum at -24.0 o C. The average annual rainfall is 236 mm, ranging from 168 mm to 308 mm over the years. Annual precipitation is mainly in winter and spring.

The type of soil in the experimental field is light gray soil.

Vegetation is based on the color brown, sagebrush, sagebrush, sagebrush, sagebrush, wormwood, sagebrush, and others.

The Nurota Experimental Field has a unique gene pool of 1,200 specimens of pasture forage plants of 50 species, brought from different soil-climatic regions of Central Asia, as well as imported by various scientific organizations through mutual seed exchange.

Prospective phytomeliorants consisting of semi-shrubs (izen, teresken, chogon) and perennial grasses (astrgal, male grass) that are resistant to shoreline from the experimental field gene pool for research The selected ones also study their economic characteristics, as

well as a comparative assessment of the productivity of natural pastures with the productivity of artificially created pastures.

One of the most important economic characteristics of pasture forage plants is the thickness and viability of the number of balls in their account plates. In the experiments, the plants died mainly in the first year of vegetation and partially in the second year. In the following years of the vegetation period, the number of plants in the field did not change. The table shows that the highest rate of survival of sprouted grasses was returned in izen (85.4%) and astragalus (81.2%), the survival rate of other species was 70.6-77.3%. is formed. These figures are high for grassland forage plants growing in extreme coastal conditions and indicate that the selected species are plants suitable for arid conditions.

Economic characteristics of pasture forage plants Nurota Experimental Field of Vegetation Vegetation 4 (2021).

No	Plant species	The number of plants in the picture is one thousand per hectare, in the den,%	Plant height, cm	Pichan yields / ga
1	Izen	18,6±0,2	94,2±3,7	17,5±0,8
		85,4		
2	Teresken	15,9±0,7	83,9± 3,5	15,8±0,6
		76,8		
3	Chogon	14,7±0,7	89,1±4,1	16,4±0,7
		73,4		
4	Weeds	15,2±0,7	74,3±3,8	14,1±0,5
		17,3		
5	Astragal	17,5±0,5	86,5±3,9	16,8±1,6

		81,2		
6	Male grass	22,8±1,1	64,2±2,8	11,5±0,4
		70,6		

The highest stage of growth and harvest of pasture forage plants is the third year of their vegetation, and the growth and yield in subsequent years is less or more than planned, depending on weather conditions. can be. In the fourth year of plant vegetation, the highest growth rate was recorded in izen (94.2 cm). Growth rates are 64.2-89.1 cm for other plant species. These figures are twice the height of plants in artificial pastures, where they grow naturally. Yields of pasture forage plants in the fourth year of their vegetation are 11.5-17.5 per plant species. The highest yield was observed in izenda (17.5). Assuming that the average yield of natural pastures is 3 quintals per hectare, the yield of artificial pastures is 4-6 times higher than that of natural pastures.

Conclusions.

In artificial pastures built from promising species of pasture forage plants, the survival rate of plants is high and the yield is 4-6 times higher than the yield of natural pastures.

In arid regions (deserts, hills) the creation of artificial pastures from promising types of pasture forage plants will increase pasture productivity, improve forage quality, increase the number of new forage species in the vegetation cover, as well as these established crops have been used for many years and the pastures are enriched with new forage plant species.

List of used literature.

1. Maxmudov M.M., Sindarov J.Q., Xalilov X.T. Adir mintaqasi yaylovlari holatini yaxshilovchi istiqbolli fitomeliorantlar // Yaylovlardan oqilona foydalanish va muhofaza qilishning institutsionar masalalari. Toshkent. 2013. 275-279 b.
2. Xalilov X.T., Sindarov J.Q., Boboeyva A.S. Yaylov ozuqabop o'simliklari genofondidan tabiiy yaylovlar holatini yaxshilashda foydalanish //Oziq-ovqat

- xavsizligi : milliy va global omillar II-xalqoro ilmiy nazariy konferentsiya. Samarqand 2020. 546-548 b.
3. Q.S. Yarashev, Samyayev A.Q., Quyi Zarafshon tuproq qoplamining inson ta'sirida o'zgarishi //Quyi Amudaryo region ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muamolarining geografik yechimlari. Respublik ilmiy –amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari. Urganch, 2010 – B. 165-168.
 4. Q.S. Yarashev. Адир тоғолди пролювиал текислик микропарагенетик ландшафт комплекси. //Ўзбекистон география жамияти IX съезди материаллари. –Тошкент, 2014. –Б. 128-129.
 5. Q.S. Yarashev, Нодирова З.Зарафшон ботиғининг табиий шароити ва воҳа ландшафтлари. //Кўҳна ва новқирон география. Тошкент, 2009. –Б. 61-63
 6. Q.S. Yarashev, Назаров Х.Т., Холмирзаев Ж.Э., Тоғ яйловларини оптималлаштиришнинг айрим масалалари. //Қишлоқ хўжалигига инновацион технологияларни жорий қилиш муаммолари. Халқаро конференция материаллари. Т. 2. -Самарқанд, 2012.